

Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia at Delphi

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Entry tags: Graeco-Roman, Greece, Hellenistic Religions, Sacred Enclosure, Temple, Temenos, Monument, Religious Place, Greek Religions, Greek Cult, Polytheistic, Aegean, Archaeological site, Religious Group, Ancient Mediterranean

On the road to Delphi, as one approaches the sanctuary of Apollo from the East (800 m from the main sanctuary), there is a much smaller sanctuary dedicated to Athena Pronaia ("Athena before the Temple") on a terrace now called "Marmaria" (150 m x 40 m). It consists of a walled temenos (sacred precinct) and various structures (altars, at least two temples, a tholos, and two treasuries). This smaller sanctuary to Athena served as a gateway to the much larger sanctuary to Apollo, and the goddess Athena can be perceived as protecting her younger half-brother, Apollo.

Date Range: 750 BCE - 395 CE

Region: Marmaria

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Eastern Mediterranean, Greece, Aegean, Central Greece, Phokis

A terrace (150 m x 40 m) on which the Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia at Delphi stood. It is located on the southern slopes of Mount Parnassos. The terrace is called "Marmaria" ("place of marble") in modern times, referring to the stone blocks scattered throughout the site prior to excavation.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bommelaer, J-F. *Marmaria : le sanctuaire d'Athéna à Delphes*. Athens, 1997.
- Source 2: Bommelaer, J.-F. *Guide de Delphes: le site*. Paris, 1991.
- Source 3: Michaud, J.-P. *Fouilles de Delphes. Tome II, le sanctuaire d'Athéna Pronaia: le temple en calcaire*. Paris, 1977.

Notes: Bookidis, N. "The Priest's House in the Marmaria at Delphi." *BCH* 107.1 (1983): 149-155. Bousquet, J. "La destination de la Tholos de Delphes." *Revue Historique*. 223.2 (1960): 287-298. Daux, G. *Fouilles de Delphes Tome II (3e fascicule), le sanctuaire d'Athéna Pronaia: les deux trésors*. Paris, 1977. de la Coste-Messelière, P. *Delphes*. Paris, 1957. Demangel, R. *Fouilles de Delphes Tome II (5e fascicule), le sanctuaire d'Athéna Pronaia: topographie du sanctuaire*. Paris, 1977. --- *Fouilles de Delphes Tome II (3e fascicule)*,

le sanctuaire d'Athèna Pronaia: les temples de tuf. Paris, 1977. Fingarette, A. "The Marmaria Puzzles." *AJA* 74.4 (1970): 401-404. Ito, J. et al. *New Measurements and Observations of the Treasury of Massaliotes, the Doric Treasury and the Tholos in the Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia at Delphi*. Tokyo, 2004. LaRoche, D. "La Tholos de Delphes : forme et destination." *Delphes: centenaire de la « Grande Fouille »* réalisée par l'École Française d'Athènes (1892-1903). Strasbourg, 1991. LeRoy, C. "Pausanias à Marmaria (XXVIII)." *BCH Suppl. IV: Études Delphiques*. 247-271. Müller, S. "Delphes mycénienne : un réexamen du site dans son contexte regional." *Delphes: centenaire de la « Grande Fouille »* réalisée par l'École Française d'Athènes (1892-1903). Strasbourg, 1991. Mulliez, M., P. Jockey, M. Vincitore, "Virtual Reconstruction and Experimental Attempt in Archaeology. The Massalian Treasury in Delphi." *Digital Heritage 2* (2013): 579-585. Pedley, J. *Sanctuaries and the Sacred in the Ancient Greek World*. Cambridge, 2005. Roux, G. *Delphes : son oracle et ses dieux*. Paris, 1976. Scott, M. *Delphi and Olympia: the Spatial Politics of Panhellenism in the Archaic and Classical Periods*. Cambridge, 2010.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=4933
- Source 1 Description: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture's description of the site
- Source 2 URL: <https://delphi.culture.gr/archaeological-site/monuments/>
- Source 2 Description: The official website of the Archaeological Site of Delphi

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1838, 1900-1902, 1938

Notes: The site of Delphi, in the 18th century, was occupied by the village of Kastri. In order to excavate the site, the whole settlement had to be demolished and the population relocated to its current location just west of the site. Kastri was renamed Delphoi. 1838 - The French School carried out sondages at the site, revealing architectural remains. When the "Grande Fouille" of Delphi began in 1892, the Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia, being of lesser importance than the main sanctuary of Apollo, did not immediately receive attention. 1900-1902 - The excavations at the turn of the century were led by Théophile Homolle, first by reopening the sondages of 1838. The majority of the excavations were conducted in 1901. After the "Grande Fouille" to the present, occasional smaller-scale excavations are carried out on site. The work conducted in 1938 was primarily concerned with the partial restoration/reconstruction of the Tholos (the round building).

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Fouilles de Delphes

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The site was located on the southern slopes of Mount Parnassos.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Trackway or road-surface

Notes: A primitive polygonal retaining wall was built to the north and east (the area sloped northwards) in the 7th c. BC, as well as a longer enclosure wall to the south. The site of Marmaria was originally a natural terrace, which was levelled, expanded, and walled after 548 BC.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The site was close to the settlement of Delphi (roughly 1.5 km to the west), which was not a major urban centre. The surrounding landscape was largely rural.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The road leading past the sanctuary was a major route through Central Greece, despite its location in a very mountainous terrain.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: It was close to several settlements (Delphi, Krisa, Kirrha, Antikyra, etc.) but I wouldn't call any of them "non-religious" since the concept of religion is anachronistic in an ancient Greek context (religion was embedded in every aspect of life) and no settlement could have been considered "non-religious".

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: During the sanctuary's first architectural phase, there was only one temple in the precinct built in the mid-7th c. BC.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 750 BCE - 548 BCE

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The earliest temple is not well-preserved as it is largely underneath the 6th c. temple. We do know that it was oriented NW-SE (an orientation which would be rotated several degrees in the 6th c. rebuilding), as its SE corner has been excavated, in addition to fragments from 12 different columns. It has been suggested that the building was hexa-amphiprostyle (6 columns only on the two short ends); however, that reconstruction is too optimistic as it assumes that we have found all of the columns.

– No

Notes: From the late 6th c. BC onwards, the sanctuary ceased to have only one single structure, as it would also be fitted with a brand new temple to replace the previous one destroyed in 548, an expanded terrace and peribolos, a more monumental altar, a treasury, and a hestiatorion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 548 BCE - 395 CE

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: NA

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The earliest structure was a temple to Athena built in the mid-7th c. BC, which was destroyed by fire in 548 BC. It was rebuilt in the 6th c. BC as a Doric peripteral temple (6 x 12 columns, tufa on top of limestone foundations) with a pronaos that was distyle in antis, and with no opisthodomos. This temple was heavily damaged during the Persian invasion, not by the Persians themselves but by a rock slide that ultimately defeated the Persian sack of Delphi. There is evidence for several modifications and repairs to this temple. It was ultimately destroyed by an earthquake in 373 BC. It may have been too structurally unsound to rebuild and was left as a ruin. The replacement temple to Athena was built roughly 50 m west of the original in the second half of the 6th c. BC, with a different plan (Doric prostyle hexastyle, limestone). The dating is disputed but falls between 375-350 BC (most likely around 360). Immediately west of the first temple to Athena are two treasuries, the Aiolic Treasury and the Doric treasury. The Aiolic treasury (distyle in antis, eastern Ionic style) was an ornately decorated building (Aiolic capitals in the form of palm leaves, bead and reel, Ionic frieze, lotus and palmettes, etc.), probably dedicated by the Massaliots (i.e. inhabitants of Massalia, the Greek name of Marseille) after their victory either over the Carthaginians or the Etruscans possibly sometime in 535-530 BC. Less than a metre to the east of the Aiolic Treasury is the slightly larger Doric treasury (distyle in antis, Doric order, Pentelic marble). It was a typical Doric structure (more austere than Ionic) and acts almost as a foil to the Aiolic treasury. It was probably dedicated by the Athenians after one of the two Persian invasions and can date between 490-460 BC (and perhaps more precisely between 475-470). Stelai were erected around the two treasuries, forming a sort of peribolos around it. To the west and partially under the second temple to Athena is a two-chambered building with both chambers facing a common porch. It was traditionally referred to as "The Priest's House" but has been interpreted as a hestiatorion or dining hall based on similarities to other hestiatoria that are close in plan (Athens, Perachora, Corinth) with more certain identifications. It was built sometime in the 6th c. BC and must have been destroyed sometime in the 4th c. BC as the second temple to Athena would be built on top of it. The most famous and most well-preserved building in this sanctuary, however, is the tholos (round building), built sometime in the Late Classical period immediately west of the Aiolic Treasury. It had an exterior colonnade of 20 Doric columns, a round cella, an interior colonnade of 20 columns (mixture of early Corinthian, Doric, and Ionic elements). Vitruvius names the architect of this building to be Theodoros of Phokaia. It was well decorated (Doric frieze but depicting the Amazonomachy on the metopes, lion gargoyles, lotus and acanthus motifs on the gutter, Lesbian moulding, door probably fitted with ivory, etc.). The date of the building is problematic with disputed dates ranging between the Late 5th to the early 4th c. BC, although probably after 375 BC. The function is even more debated (Thiersch: musical performances; Poulsen: heroon to Phylakos; Pomtow: Prytaneion; Homolle: repository for statues of Roman emperors; Bousquet: Artemision). There is no consensus. In addition to these buildings, there was also a great altar (originally earthen). It was originally to the east of the 7th c. temple. After the temple was rebuilt in situ in the 6th c., the altar was also elaborated (large polygonal limestone blocks bordering a platform, beside which a thick layer of bones and ash were excavated. There was also a smaller terrace in the northeast corner of the precinct, hanging above the sanctuary, which contained two very small buildings (one of which was perhaps the heroon of Phylakos). There was also a monumental base placed in front of the two treasuries between 350-300 BC, perhaps where the polis of Delphi placed the victory monument commemorating the miraculous defeat of the Persians.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The site had several construction phases as it was very prone to destruction by earthquakes and landslides. There were major construction phases in the mid-7th, 6th, and 4th c. BC.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

– Social

– Memorial

– Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: The first temple was destroyed by fire in 548 BC.

– Collapsed

Notes: The first temple was damaged during the Persian invasion by an earthquake. It was rebuilt but was then destroyed by an earthquake in 373 BC. It was not rebuilt after this as it may have been determined to be too structurally dangerous to restore. A new temple was built a few metres to the west.

–Other [specify]: Abandoned

Notes: The proscription against pagan sanctuaries in the 4th c. AD brought an end to the sanctuaries at Delphi.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- For religious reasons
- As the result of war
- As the result of pillage

Notes: In this question, I refer to three separate events. "As a result of war/pillage" refers to two events: the attempted destruction of the sanctuary by the Persians in 480 BC, which caused damage to the sanctuary but was not an utter destruction, and to the Gallic invasion of Greece in 279 BC, during which the Gauls attempted to sack Delphi but were repelled by a thunderstorm allowing the Greeks to drive them back (Pausanias and Justin) to the Spercheios River Valley where they were fully defeated by the Thessalians and the Malians. "For religious reasons" refers to the official proscription against paganism in the 390s AD under Theodosius. When this region became Christian, the sanctuary was de-sacralized. We know, for example, that the Doric treasury was being used as a small house (into the floor of which a pithos was dug), that Christian lamps began to be found all over the sanctuary, and that people searching for metal pillaged the sanctuary in the Late Roman period.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

- Natural phenomena

Notes: This does not refer to the final destruction of the sanctuary, which came about because of the proscription against paganism but to the first destruction of the 7th c. temple (fire), the second destruction (earthquake), and the 480 BC rock slide.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

- Yes

↳ In antiquity

- More than once

Notes: The 7th c. temple was reconstructed in the same place in the 6th c. BC, and then reconstructed further to the west in the 4th c. BC.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The tholos was partially reconstructed (three columns and part of the architrave) in 1938.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Athena Pronaia

Notes: Athena Pronaia was the primary deity, but there were also subsidiary deities worshipped at the sanctuary that are attested in inscriptions (Eileithyia, Hygieia, Zeus Polieus, Athena Ergane, Athena Zosteria).

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: In addition to Athena Pronaia, inscribed dedications to Eileithyia, Hygieia, Zeus Polieus, Athena Ergane, Athena Zosteria have been found at the site.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias says that there was a heroon (Paus. 10.8.7) to Phylakos who defended Delphi against the invading Persians in 480 with his brother Autonoos (Hdt. 8.38-39).

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: Although Pausanias says that it was a heroon to Pausanias, it is assumed that it was also dedicated to his brother, Autonoos, with whom he defended Delphi.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Polis of Delphi

Notes: Unlike the Sanctuary of Apollo, which was administered by an international league called the Delphic Amphiktyony, the Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia was administered solely by the polis of Delphi.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Slaves

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: resident foreigners

Notes: We know that the sanctuary was administered by the polis of Delphi but that specific states and families often financed the building of the structures and monuments in it. The city of Massalia financed the building of the Aiolic Treasury and the Athenians funded the Doric treasury. It is possible that the 6th c. temple was made with the assistance of the Alkmaionidai, an aristocratic Athenian family who contributed to many monuments at Delphi in the Late Archaic period. We know that specialized architects and sculptors worked on the various buildings, not only by the quality of the surviving architectural and sculptural elements but also through the literary sources, which name, for example, Theodoros of Phokaia as the architect of the Tholos. In Athenian building accounts, metics (resident foreigners), citizens, and slaves worked on public buildings in Attica. It is probable that all three served as builders at Delphi as well.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Ge, Apollo, Python

Notes: In the foundation myth of Delphi, the whole site was originally a precinct of Ge/Gaia (the site of what would be the sanctuary of Apollo was believed to be Ge's navel or "omphalos"). The sanctuary of Ge was guarded by Python, whom Apollo slays. The sanctuary then becomes a sanctuary of Apollo. The sanctuary of Athena Pronaia would be built as a subsidiary sanctuary guarding the entrance to the main sanctuary of Apollo.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Oracle

Notes: The main sanctuary of Apollo began as an oracular sanctuary, and as the sanctuary of Athena Pronaia was created as a fore-sanctuary to Apollo's, I would extend that event to the Pronaia sanctuary.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: We know that the Massaliots and the Athenians financed specific buildings in the sanctuary, and Roman emperors later donated to it.

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: The construction of a Greek sanctuary or the donation of structures to a sanctuary often implied the reciprocal expectation of the deity's favour.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: As the sanctuary is on a terrace (natural but artificially expanded) on a mountain slope,

the whole sanctuary is associated with a landscape feature. It has a retaining wall that holds back against the slope in the north and east of the sanctuary.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Notes: The various buildings and monuments at this site are all free-standing.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of ritual, the great altar would be the most important structure at the sanctuary as it is one of the two essential elements of a sanctuary (the other being the bounded space itself). It would rank higher than the smaller altars to the subsidiary deities in the sanctuary. Among the buildings, the temple would be the most important as it houses the cult image. In terms of prestige, the tholos might rank the highest as it was the most architecturally innovative, but would always be secondary in religious importance. The treasuries and all other subsidiary buildings would rank lower in importance although they did bring prestige to the states/individuals that funded their construction.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 40

Notes: The percentage I gave is a visual estimate of the amount of space taken up by the various structures (at the sanctuary's greatest extent in the 4th c. BC) in comparison to the dimensions of the narrow precinct. I include the space taken up by the destroyed Archaic temple, as a ruin left in place can also be considered a monument (e.g. the Archaic temple of Athena on the Acropolis that was destroyed by the Persians and left as a monument for the remainder of antiquity).

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 363.71

Notes: The number refers to the 6th c. BC temple. The actual dimensions, at the level of the stylobate is 27.45 x 13.25 m.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 13.5

Notes: The height given does not belong to the 6th c. BC temple, which was the largest in terms of area, as its height is unknown, but is probably not taller than the Tholos. The height of the 4th c. BC temple is also unknown but estimated at 6.21 m. The height given belongs to the Tholos, which was probably the tallest monument on site.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 160.13

Notes: 6th c. BC temple: $27.45 \times 13.25 = 363.71$ Doric Treasury: $6.60 \text{ m} \times 9.74 = 64.28$ Aiolic Treasury: $6.14 \times 8.40 = 51.58$ 4th c. BC temple: $10.82 \times 18.95 = 205.04$ Tholos: $13.50 \text{ m diameter} = 143.14$ Hestiatorion ("Priest's House"): $12.15 \times 10.95 = 133.04$ The measurements do not include the smaller altars and other small structures, and so this number really refers to the size of the average building. Although the 6th and 4th c. temples were not in concurrent use, I included the dimensions of both, as a temple left in ruins can still be considered a monument.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The original altar was an earthen altar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 750 BCE - 548 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The internal structures of the various buildings were partially of wood but those do not survive.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes
– No

Notes: Some of the limestone is sourced locally (the local stone coming from the Profitis Ilias quarry), but others were imported.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: NA

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Parts of the buildings were made of metal clamps.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Ionic frieze on the Aiolic Treasury depicted an Amazonomachy and a Gigantomachy, the latter of which is a battle between the gods and the giants.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Centaurs and giants are depicted.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Amazons, Lapiths, statues of Roman emperors,

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Horses (in the Amazonomachy relief on the Tholos), lions (as gargoyles on the

Tholos).

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Centaurs

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: If triglyphs and bead-and-reel count as geometric.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Acanthus leaves, palmettes, lotuses, etc.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: NA

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there was presumably a xoanon as there was a temple.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: It does not survive but the xoanon would have been of Athena Pronaia. Pausanias (Paus. 10.8.6) states that the temple of Athena had two statues, one in the

interior and a larger one dedicated by the Massaliots in the pronaos (τῶν δὲ ἀγαλμάτων τὸ ἐν τῷ προνάῳ Μασσαλιωτῶν ἀνάθημά ἐστι, μεγέθει τοῦ ἔνδον ἀγάλματος μεῖζον.). There was also a statue of Athena possibly dedicated by the Athenians, placed within the Tholos.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Pausanias writes that one of the buildings held statues of Roman emperors. There was also a statue of Callipus by Cyzicus transferred to the Tholos.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The reliefs from the Tholos and the Aiolic Treasury are fragmentary. They may or may not have depicted Athena. However, I answered yes as the Aiolic Treasury contained a Gigantomachy relief and Athena's defeat of the giant Enkelados is commonly depicted in Gigantomachies.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Amazonomachy, Centauromachy, Gigantomachy.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Floral motifs in relief

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Type
 - Secco
 - Other [specify]: Technically all the reliefs on the buildings would have been painted.

- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - Yes

- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - No

- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: NA

- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No

- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - No

- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative [e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Pausanias mentions a golden shield dedicated by King Kroisos (Croesus of Lydia)

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: Unless one counts the superhuman heroes, Autoonoos and Phylakos.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: I do want to add that one of the necropoleis of Delphi was found further to the east of this sanctuary but was not related to its cult.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: Technically Zeus was also worshipped as a chthonic deity in addition to being a sky god (with the epithets Ktesios and Meilichios for example).

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Many elite families claim descent from Zeus through a semi-divine ancestor but if I restrict that to the region of Phokis, then no.

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: NA

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Not at the Sanctuary of Athena Pronaia, but 1 km up the road to the Sanctuary of Apollo is the famous Oracle.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: There was an agalma of Athena at the pronaos of the temple.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, as access to the inside of a temple is restricted and so the xoanon inside would not have been visible at all times.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer, ritual, sacrifice, etc.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There was at least one heroon on the site, according to Pausanias.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Constantly

Notes: There was a large deposit of ash and bone beside the great altar.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Statues (many dedicated by victors of the Pythian Games), precious metals, war booty, etc. The fact that there were treasuries at the sanctuary also means that the states that dedicated them also filled them with votives.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: There was a bothros (circular pit) in the western part of the sanctuary.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: NA

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: This is an assumption on my part but one that seems self-evident.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
 - Notes: We have evidence of repairs and renovations from several of the buildings.
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: NA

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - optional (common)

- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - Yes

Notes: Although the ultimate destination of a pilgrim would be to the Sanctuary of Apollo further up the road, the Pronaia sanctuary served as a gateway and was meant to welcome those pilgrims.

- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - No

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - Yes

- ↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
 - No

Notes: There are several pilgrimage and procession routes to Delphi, depending on the festival. The most famous is the route for the enneatric Septeria festival, which includes a procession and pilgrimage from Delphi to the Vale of Tempe (over 300 km) and back to Delphi. Maintenance of the roads involved would fall to the communities that occupied various stretches of the roads.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The Hestiatorion (the so-called "Priest's House")

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Monthly, Annual, Tetraeteric, Penteteric, Enneateric

Notes: These include festivals dedicated to the main sanctuary of Apollo as the Pronaia sanctuary would have been the entrance for any visitors.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: When it comes to the Pythian Games, participation was restricted to Greek-speaking males (women, slaves barred).

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Healing may not have physically taken place at this sanctuary in the same way as at an Asklepieion but requests for healing did happen as there were inscriptions to Hygieia (goddess associated with healing) and Eilythyia (goddess of childbirth) were found at the sanctuary.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: If wine counts, it would have been present during various rituals.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: As a general rule, Greek priests and priestesses matched the gender of the deity they served.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: Greek. Whether they were always Delphian is uncertain.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Greek priesthoods were served on a limited-term basis as there was no professional priesthood in Greece. There were very few lifetime Greek priesthoods and the cult of Athena Pronaia did not have one.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Hestiatorion was originally interpreted as a "Priest's House" but architectural similarities to other buildings with more certain functions have shown that it was more likely a dining hall.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The polis of Delphi. Less formal than the Delphic Amphiktyony but still formal.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: Contrast the situation with the Sanctuary of Apollo which had sacred territories extending far beyond the temenos.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No